

Integrated Analysis of Physico-Chemical and Biological Parameters in Water Quality Assessment of Musi River

Lakhya Sharma¹, Shruti Joshi²

^{1,2}Department of Biotechnology, St. Francis College for Women, Begumpet, Hyderabad.
Email ID: 121323051013@sfc.ac.in

Abstract:

Water is the most important natural resource maintaining different ecosystems, human activities and lives. Although, the Earth has plenty of water, only a small percentage of the freshwater is useful for humans. One of the freshwater bodies, the rivers serve as an essential source for domestic, agricultural, and industrial grounds. Nevertheless, urbanization, industrialization, population growth, and agricultural expansion is causing deterioration in the river water quality. The Musi River, tributary of the Krishna River, flowing through Hyderabad in Telangana, is one among such rivers systems that have been strongly affected by human activities. Massive amount of domestic waste, agricultural runoff, and material waste from the city is flows into the river increasing the content of nutrients, pesticides, heavy metals, and pathogenic microorganisms in it. The present study is done to assess the water quality of the Musi River by analyzing different physical, chemical, biochemical and microbial parameters. The values observed were: pH in the water sample was observed to be in the desirable limits as per the Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) (6.5- 8.5) and the TDS (Total Dissolved Solids) present in the sample were greater than the optimum limit given by the (BIS) i.e. 100- 400 ppm. There was heavy microbial load observed in the sample indicating contamination from various sewages. Positive results for certain biochemical tests pointed out the presence of various coliform bacteria found in the feces of humans. The results emphasized regular water quality monitoring and effective management to reduce pollution and protect human health.

Key words: Water quality assessment, TDS, pH, Musi River, Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS)

1. Introduction

Surface freshwater systems are some of the most important and yet, the most limited natural resources available to mankind that support human health, the agriculture we cultivate, and the stability of ecosystems (Guidelines for Drinking-Water Quality, 2011). The baseline chemistry of flowing water is determined primarily by the hydrological process; however, the rate of urban growth and land alteration continues to modify, both spatially and temporally, nutrient transport and ionic concentrations within flowing waters (Giri & Qiu, 2016; Dudgeon, 2007). The discharge

of untreated municipal effluents and industrial waste combined with the processes of diffuse runoff exacerbate pollutant loading in urban rivers and therefore change their physicochemical characteristics (Carpenter et al., 1998; UNEP, 2016).

Water quality can be adversely impacted by human input into aquatic ecosystems, with concentrations of dissolved solids, nitrogen-containing compounds and trace metals often exceeding their "background" levels (Singh et al., 2012; Raj et al., 2011). The input of organic matter into an aquatic system promotes the development of microbial populations that increase aerobic respiration. In many cases this will be seen as low dissolved oxygen (DO), and considerable increases in biochemical (BOD) and chemical (COD) oxygen demand (Chapman, 1996) (Chapman, 2021) (Sharma & Kansal, 2011). Therefore, pH, temperature, total dissolved solids (TDS), dissolved oxygen (DO), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), and chemical oxygen demand (COD) are routinely measured to assess the health of aquatic ecosystems (APHA, 2017; BIS, 2012). Composite indices and multivariate analytic tools are used to evaluate the spatial and temporal distribution of physical and chemical variability in rivers (Tyagi et al., 2013; Singh et al., 2012) (Tyagi et al., 2020).

In India, metropolitan river ecosystems are showing increasing signs of ecological degradation caused by the rapid population increase and inadequate wastewater treatment capacity (CPCB, 2022)(Mishra and Tripathi 2007). The Musi River, which begins in the Ananthagiri Hills and runs through the city of Hyderabad, is an urban river that is subject to continual human pressure. Past studies have shown increased organic load, changed ionic balance, and accumulated heavy metals in the river and its accompanying water-soil-plant continuum (Sujatha 2016; Raj et al. 2011; Pulikkal et al. 2025) (Sujatha 2016). Analyses have also shown elevated ammonia and bicarbonate concentrations and altered oxygen conditions (Subbarao et al. 2016). Changes like these may affect agriculture lands irrigated by the river and the ecological integrity of downstream ecosystems (Ayers and Westcot 1985)(Bhutiani et al. 2016).

Water contamination by microbes is an additional factor willing to lead to poor water quality. The presence of coliform bacteria in the water is seen as an indicator of faecal contamination and reduced sanitary conditions (WHO, 2017; APHA, 2017) (Guidelines for Drinking Water Quality, 2011b). Evidence suggests that as rivers become increasingly enriched with organic matter, the levels of microorganisms rise, thereby increasing the public health risks to those who depend upon these waterways for their needs (Mishra and Tripathi, 2008) (Venkatesharaju et al., 1970). The Bureau of Indian Standards defines maximum acceptable limits for drinking water; therefore any sample exceeding these limits is unsuitable for domestic use (BIS, 2012) (DrinWatIS10500, n.d.).

Comprehensive evaluation of river systems therefore requires integration of physical observation, chemical quantification, and microbiological investigation within a structured monitoring framework (APHA, 2017)(Chapman, 2021). Sustained surveillance of urban rivers

such as the Musi is essential for evidence-based pollution mitigation strategies and long-term environmental protection (UNEP, 2016; CPCB, 2022).

2. Materials and methods

Collection of Water Sample:

To avoid external contaminants samples of water from the Musi river at Puranapool Hyderabad were collected with sterilized sampling containers. Geographic coordinates date and time of collection were recorded with the use of a gps-based mobile app the collected samples were then transferred to a laboratory for further analysis regarding physiochemistry microbiology and biochemistry in detail.

Physical Parameters:

Immediately after collecting the sample, the evaluation of few physical parameters was performed at the site of the sample collection. Colour, turbidity, pH, water temperature, and total dissolved solids (TDS) were the parameters analyzed. Colour and turbidity readings were taken by visually assessing the sample provided. The pH was determined using a calibrated digital pH meter and glass electrode to measure the activity of (H^+) ions in the sample solution. The reading was recorded when the instrument showed a stable reading, ensuring accuracy. A digital thermometer was used to measure the temperature of the water sample accurately. A TDS meter, which works based on the conductivity of electricity through water, was used to estimate the TDS content of the sample. This is accomplished by measuring the conductivity of water to determine the dissolved salts/minerals concentration in the sample.

Chemical Parameters:

The current study included estimation of heavy metal ions, alkalinity and oxygen related parameters under chemical assessment by using titrimetric analysis. The reaction for Ammonia and Bicarbonates estimation is an Acid-Base titration where the ammonium ions and bicarbonate ions respectively neutralize the acids they are titrated against. Methyl orange is used as an indicator for both but sample for estimation of ammonia is titrated against N/10 HCl and against N/20 H_2SO_4 for bicarbonates estimation. The Total Hardness is calculated by estimating both the ions responsible for the hardness of water which are Calcium and Magnesium ions. The method used for their estimation is EDTA titrations where EBT is used as an indicator and the samples are titrated against 0.1M EDTA. Method used to determine Zinc concentration is Complexometric titration, where the EBT (indicator) in the metal ion complex is replaced by the EDTA present in the burette forming a new colorless complex. The amount of oxygen content in water the DO of water and BOD the amount of oxygen consumed by the organisms in water both were done using Manganese Sulphate (2.15M) to fix the oxygen in water, Alkaline Iodide (1270 g/L) that gives precipitate, H_2SO_4 (29%) to dissolve the precipitate, 1% starch as indicator and titrated

the sample against Sodium Thiosulphate (Hypo) of 0.0025N. In order to estimate the correct amount of BOD, 25ml of water sample is also incubated for 5 days followed by the procedure. COD that gives correct information about organic matter in the water sample is estimated by their oxidizability. The chemicals used here are Potassium Dichromate (chemical oxidant) Potassium iodide (10%), H_2SO_4 (10%) and 1% starch as indicator titrated against Hypo (Sodium Thiosulphate) of normality 0.1N.

Microbial Parameters:

Microbiological assessment involved staining and selective culture techniques to evaluate bacterial diversity and contamination. Gram staining was performed to differentiate bacterial isolates based on staining characteristics, categorizing them as Gram-positive or Gram-negative depending on colour retention.

Selective and differential culture media were employed to identify potential enteric organisms. MacConkey agar (5.0%) was used to distinguish lactose-fermenting from non-lactose-fermenting bacteria based on colony colour changes. Eosin Methylene Blue (EMB) (3.6%) agar was used to detect Gram-negative lactose fermenters and observe characteristic colony morphology after incubation. All plating procedures were carried out using the streak plate method to obtain isolated colonies for further analysis.

Biochemical Parameters:

Biochemical analysis of water was done under 5 parameters. The oxidase test uses a disc containing tetramethyl-p-phenylenediamine (TMPD), onto which bacterial colonies are applied. A purple colour change indicates the presence of cytochrome-c-oxidase, suggesting aerobic respiratory activity. Catalase test is a test where 3% H_2O_2 is dropped on the bacterial colonies to test for the presence of catalase enzyme which is indicated positive by observing the effervescence produced. H_2S production test is done to identify whether the bacterial colonies produce H_2S gas. It is performed on the Kligler Iron Agar which turns black if the gas is produced by the glucose metabolism of the bacterial colonies. IMViC test is a set of tests that determine the species of the bacterial coliforms in the water sample. In the indole test, bacteria are grown in tryptophan broth; organisms producing tryptophanase break it down to form indole. Addition of Kovac's reagent produces a violet ring, indicating a positive result. Methyl red test is a test for bacterial species that use acid fermentation method for glucose metabolism. The bacteria are grown in MR-VP broth (glucose source) then on addition of Methyl-red indicator if the culture turns red it indicated a positive result. For Voges-Proskauer test the sample is first inoculated in MR-VP broth then alpha-naphthol and 40% NaOH are added. If the sample turn violet it indicates the breakdown of pyruvate to acetoin which is a positive result. In Citrate test the bacteria are tested if they can use citrate as their only carbon source and if the agar turns blue from green then it indicates a positive result.

3. Results

Physical analysis:

Table 1: Physical Analysis

Parameters	Observed values	Standard values
pH	8.12	6.5-8.5
Temperature	26.1	10°C-30°C
TDS	314	100-400ppm

Fig 1: Color and Turbidity

Chemical analysis:

Table 2: Chemical Analysis

Parameters	Observed Values	Standard values
Ammonia	0.59mg/L	0.5mg/L
Total Hardness(Ca ⁺² ,Mg ⁺²)	Ca ⁺² =0.16mg/L,Mg ⁺² =0.09 mg/L	75mg/L;30mg/L
Zinc	0.26mg/L	5.0mg/L
Bicarbonates	268.47ppm	200ppm
DO	4.85mg/L	6.5-8mg/L
BOD	4.92mg/L	2-3mg/L
COD	36.8mg/L	20g/L

Microbial analysis:

Results:

Fig 2: Gram Staining

Fig 3: MacConkey Agar

Fig 4: EMB Agar

Biochemical analysis:

Results:

Fig 5: Oxidase Test

Fig 6: Catalase Test

Fig 7: Kligler Iron Agar

Fig 8: IMViC- Indole, Methyl red, Voges Proskauer, Citrate

4. Discussions

Water sample from Musi River was assessed under various physical, chemical, microbial and biochemical parameters and compared to the standard values given by BIS (Bureau of Indian Standards).

Physical analysis:

The physical properties taken into account when assessing the quality of drinking water were total dissolved solids (TDS), turbidity, pH, colour and temperature. Water appeared clear and did not have visible turbidity; therefore, it is likely to be in a constant state of flow. The sample had a pH of 8.21 and was within the acceptable BIS range (6.5 - 8.5); however, it is slightly alkaline. TDS for this review was 314 ppm and temperature was 26.1 °C which are both acceptable values. While all of these parameters met the BIS standard, TDS and pH being slightly elevated indicate that there may have been an increase in the concentration of ions (for example: ammonia). Such a change may affect the physical, chemical, or biological characteristics of the water being tested.

Chemical analysis:

The analysis of the water sample was performed using the standard tests for determining ammonia, total hardness (calcium & magnesium), zinc, bicarbonates, and oxygen parameters

(DO, BOD, and COD). The results showed that the ammonia concentration of 0.59 mg/L was slightly above the recommended limit. The concentrations of calcium (0.16 mg/L) and magnesium (0.09 mg/L) were very low indicating that the water is extremely soft and lacks the minerals essential for drinking. The bicarbonate level of 268.7 ppm should be considered excessive causing increased alkalinity. The dissolved oxygen level was 4.85 mg/L while the BOD (4.92 mg/L) and COD (36.8 mg/L) levels were above the acceptable limits. The elevated BOD and COD values demonstrate organic pollution and high levels of bacterial activity in the water. The overabundance of organic matter in the river will cause health concerns associated with respiratory and gastrointestinal ailments.

Microbial analysis:

Optimization of bacterial load and diversity determination of river water was done via a combination of three principle methods. The first method was a Gram stain which differentiated bacterial isolates based upon the composition of their cell walls. The microscopic examination revealed that there were many purple stained cells. This indicates that there was a greater number of gram-positive organisms present and, correspondingly a lesser number of pink stained (gram negative) organisms. The second and third methods for assessment of potential pathogenic contamination included selective and differential culturing using MacConkey and Eosin Methylene Blue (EMB) agar. The development of pink colonies on MacConkey agar exhibited the presence of lactose fermenting gram negative enteric bacteria. The metallic green sheen of colonies grown on EMB is indicative of rapid and heavy lactose fermentation. The observation of these colonies would suggest a potential pathogenic fecal contamination of the water from untreated domestic wastewater discharge. In contrast, there were no gram-negative bacteria grown which exhibited no color change (lactose fermenters) on either type of media. Overall, these microbial indicators are potential evidence that the water may pose a health risk if used for irrigation or fishing. Long term exposure to potential pathogens from this water could result in illnesses with neurological effects as well as disruptions to other organ systems.

Biochemical analysis:

Biochemical tests were carried out to confirm the bacterial species present in the river water sample from Musi River. The Oxidase and Catalase tests were performed first, and both showed positive results. A positive oxidase test was indicated by the development of a purple colour on the disc within one minute, confirming the presence of the oxidase enzyme, while immediate effervescence on adding hydrogen peroxide confirmed a positive catalase reaction. The Kligler Iron Agar test also showed a positive result with blackening of the medium, indicating H₂S gas production. IMViC tests were conducted for further identification: Indole and Methyl Red tests were positive (violet ring formation and red colour respectively), whereas Voges–Proskauer and Citrate tests were negative (no blue colour change and no shift of green medium to blue). Based on these biochemical characteristics, the likely faecal coliforms contributing to pollution include

Escherichia coli, *Enterobacter*, *Klebsiella*, *Pseudomonas*, *Citrobacter*, *Campylobacter*, *Salmonella*, *Proteus*, and *Shigella*, indicating significant faecal contamination and microbial pollution in the river water.

Conclusion

A combined evaluation of the physicochemical, microbial, and biochemical characteristics demonstrates that the Musi River water at Puranapool is subject to significant organic and microbial pollution. Increased values of BOD, COD, and ammonia, along with the detection of faecal coliforms, indicate substantial contamination, even though certain physical parameters fall within permissible standards. Such conditions point toward possible ecological disturbance and associated public health risks. Continuous surveillance and effective wastewater treatment strategies are therefore necessary to safeguard and rehabilitate the river ecosystem.

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